

PECULIARITIES OF TAXING THE INCOME OF INDIVIDUAL ENTREPRENEURS

Tillanazarov Zuhridin To'xtamurod's son

Namangan state university

Faculty of Economics

3-course student

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Abstract: This article deals with the procedure of taxation of individual entrepreneurs. Also, the opinions of taxpayers were gathered based on a survey conducted on social networks about income declaration. Based on the objective necessity of the declaration mechanism, proposals were made to expand its coverage in the country.

Key words: Income tax of individuals, mechanism of declaration, taxation of income based on declaration, unification of taxes, simplification of tax reports, hidden economy.

INTRODUCTION

Documents related to tax legislation issued in Uzbekistan over the past 3 years, in particular, the new Tax Code, Decrees of the President of the Republic of Uzbekistan No. PF-4947 of February 7, 2017, PF-6098 of October 30, 2020, 2021 of the Cabinet of Ministers On the basis of decisions No. 1 of January 7, introducing modern methods of tax administration, reducing the level of the hidden economy, creating equal competitive conditions for conducting business activities at the expense of reducing the tax burden, continuing the policy of simplifying the taxation system, creating favorable conditions for conducting business activities and Measures to improve the investment environment have been determined, and a number of works are being carried out to unify taxes and simplify tax reports, while ensuring the completeness of tax revenues to the state budget in these areas.[1] In particular, the relevant articles of the new version of the Tax Code should be added to the types of income taxed on the basis of the declaration widely used in the practice of developed countries (income received by individual entrepreneurs, their hired workers, family members of a family entrepreneur, members of a trade association) with the long-awaited next step in the practice of income tax assessment through the declaration mechanism.[2]

Taxation of individual entrepreneurs

According to the Tax Code of the Republic of Uzbekistan, individual entrepreneurs pay taxes in the following order:

Income from the sale of goods (services) in the calendar year I. 100 mln. Individual entrepreneurs whose income does not exceed soum pay income tax in two ways:

- 1) pay tax in fixed amounts every month;
- 2) may pay income tax by submitting a declaration to the state tax inspectorate at the place of permanent residence, deducting the amount of expenses related to the receipt of these incomes.

II. Income from the sale of goods (services) in a calendar year is 100 mln. more than soums, but 1 bln. individual entrepreneurs whose income does not exceed soums are transferred to pay the turnover tax (the former single tax payment).

Such entrepreneurs can also choose to pay taxes in two ways:

- The sales revenue in the calendar year is 100 mln. if it exceeds soum, to pay turnover tax on the increased amount;

- realization income in the calendar year is 100 mln. can choose to pay value added tax and profit tax instead of paying turnover tax when it exceeds soums.

III. In the calendar year, the income from the sale of goods (services) is 1 billion. individual entrepreneurs whose income exceeds soums will pay value added tax and profit tax according to the procedure established for legal entities.

Also, individual entrepreneurs who switched to paying taxes in the prescribed manner for legal entities were given the right to choose a simplified procedure for calculating profit tax.

In this case, the tax base of the simplified procedure of the profit tax is set at 25% of the total income.

When an individual entrepreneur chooses a simplified procedure for calculating profit tax, he is exempted from the obligation to keep expense accounts for the purpose of calculating the tax.[4]

LITERATURE ANALYSIS AND METHODS

According to the results of the study, Indonesia is one of the few systems that have improved the declaration system of the income and property of civil servants, that through the use of this system, the activities of civil servants are fully controlled, corruption, interests are completely conflict, money laundering and effective mechanism in combating terrorism.

In recent years, in our country, the first steps have been taken in this direction, i.e., the declaration of income of civil servants. For example, in the Decree No. PF-5729 of the President of the Republic of Uzbekistan SH.Mirziyov, the priority directions of the state policy in the field of combating corruption envisage the implementation of necessary measures related to the creation of technical infrastructure and necessary software in the medium term. measures for the step-by-step introduction of the system of declaration of incomes of civil servants were determined. If we take into account that the head of our state also emphasized the need to declare the income of civil servants as the most effective way to fight against corruption, we will be able to understand the relevance of the topic.[3]

Over the years, many Uzbek economists and researchers have regularly studied the system of taxing and declaring the income of individuals. In particular, Niyazmetov's monograph (2017) and doctoral dissertation (2018) paid special attention to the income declaration system. In particular, Niyazmetov criticized the fact that one of the factors differentiating the tax system of Uzbekistan from international tax practice is the lack of a mechanism for taxation based on the general declaration of income and the fact that the mechanism for taxation of income based on declaration in Uzbekistan is not comprehensive. Also, according to the results of the analysis, there is a high potential for increasing the share of personal income tax in the state budget in Uzbekistan, and for this, it is necessary to increase the number of taxpayers and expand the tax base. and it was scientifically concluded that the mechanism of taxing income based on the declaration is considered the most effective instrument. In addition, by Usmonova (2011), in the implementation of the need for a step-by-step transition to the general declaration system in the taxation of the income of individuals, the improvement of the existing declaration system and the expansion of the scope of taxable income based on the declaration, and all individuals with taxable income it was reported that it is necessary to introduce taxation based on declaration of annual income. In the implementation of the declaration system, development of social deductions, creation of opportunities to deduct taxes paid for property and land taxes from the income tax base, as well as restoration of the

amount of non-taxable income and bringing it closer to the consumption basket in the future suggestions are given. In this study, based on the information of the State Tax Committee and the State Statistics Committee of the Republic of Uzbekistan, information on taxpayers submitting declarations, as well as library catalogs, academic articles, Internet sources and other sources of information was studied.

In order to analyze and compare the collected data (quantitative and qualitative data), that is, to analyze the changes in indicators over the years, to carry out structural analysis, descriptive statistics and questionnaire methods of research methodology were used.

Critical analysis of personal income taxation in Uzbekistan.

According to the current tax legislation in my country, the income of individuals is taxed in 3 different ways. These are withholding tax, self-employed flat rate taxation, and declaration taxation, which yields a relatively small percentage of income tax revenue.

However, despite the implemented measures, according to the results of the analysis, the level of personal income taxation in Uzbekistan still remains at a low level (3.9% in 2020). Similarly, when analyzing the data provided by the Statistics Committee of the Republic of Uzbekistan with the available data on the number of individuals paying income tax in the State Tax Committee, the total income tax the ratio of the number of private individuals to the number of economically active population is 29.3% - 39.7% during 2016-2020 [5]

ANALYSIS AND RESULTS

The level of taxation of the population's income (prepared independently by the author based on the data of the Statistics and Tax Committee of the Republic)

* Including fully and partially exempt taxpayers' income.

** Income from work and self-produced services for personal consumption.

A 1 2 3=4+5+6 4 5 6 7=3/2*100 8

2016 14,022.40 13,298.40 3,895.9 3,800.6 95.3 29.30 9,402.5

2017 14 357.30 13 520.30 3 954.1 3 849.2 104.9 29.25 9 566.2

2018 14,641.70 13,273.10 4,060.7 3,921.6 139.1 30.59 9,212.4

2019 14,876.40 13,541.10 4,537.9 4,370.4 167.5 33.51 9,003.2

2020 14 797.92 13 239.55 5 251.8 4 481.1 211.0 559.7 39.67 7 987.8

Comparative analytical data on the number of economically active population and individuals paying income tax in 2016-2020 (independently prepared by the author)

As can be seen from the above diagram and table, the effectiveness of the system of taxation of population incomes in force in the Republic is not up to the required level. By improving and popularizing the income declaration mechanism used in the practice of developed countries of the world, we can see that there is a high possibility of more comprehensive coverage of taxpayers and their incomes, and thereby increasing the fiscal importance of income tax from individuals.

In order to receive opinions and suggestions on the existing system of taxing income based on declaration in Uzbekistan, existing problems in relation to this matter, aspects that cause difficulties for citizens in matters of taxing based on declaration, through "Google forms" (<https://docs.google.com/forms/u/0/>) a survey was organized and invited to voluntarily participate in the survey in social networks, in particular, in www.facebook.com and telegram social network groups.

A total of 21 taxpayers participated in this survey, including 3 taxpayers aged 18-30, 17 taxpayers aged 31-55 and 1 over 65 years old. Among them, 18 men and 3 women, 10 individuals with a master's degree or higher, 10 with a bachelor's degree, and 1 individual with secondary specialized education participated.[13]

A total of 21 of the people who participated in this survey have a source of income in the form of payment for labor, 1 person has income from business activities, 1 person has income from renting their property, and 1 person has income in the form of dividends and interest. income, 1 person has income from abroad, 1 person has income from the sale of their property, and 3 people have other sources of income.[6]

Fixed tax

Individual entrepreneurs whose income from the sale of goods (works, services) in a calendar year does not exceed 100 million soums pay a fixed tax.

The fixed tax is paid according to the fixed rates depending on the type of business activity and the place of activity of the taxpayer, regardless of the number of working days of an individual entrepreneur in a calendar month.

In the event that an individual entrepreneur engages in several types of activity, the fixed tax is calculated separately for each type of activity at the rates set for this type of activity.

If the fixed tax rates for the place of activity are different from the fixed rates for the place of state registration, the fixed tax is paid at the highest rate.[7]

For example, A fixed tax at the rate of 10 times the minimum wage established for the city of Tashkent in the event that an individual entrepreneur who is a state-registered retailer of non-food goods in the Zangiota district of the Tashkent region carries out his activities in the city of Tashkent will pay If this entrepreneur operates in Zangiota district, he pays tax at the rate of 3 times the minimum wage.

A newly registered individual entrepreneur, including a family business entity, pays the fixed tax from the month following the month of state registration as an individual entrepreneur.

If graduates of vocational colleges are registered as an individual entrepreneur within twelve months after graduation, they are exempted from paying a fixed tax based on the date of state registration as an individual entrepreneur. will be released for six months. If the activity is terminated within twelve months from the time of state registration as an individual entrepreneur or suspended for three or more months, the fixed tax is paid for the entire period of activity.

If the activity is terminated within twelve months from the time of state registration as an individual entrepreneur or the activity is suspended for three or more months, the fixed tax is paid for the entire period of activity.

Single tax payment and general tax payments.[12]

Individual entrepreneurs whose income from the sale of goods (works, services) in a calendar year exceeds 100 million soums, but does not exceed one billion soums, are transferred to pay a single tax payment.

Individual entrepreneurs whose income from the sale of goods (works, services) does not exceed one billion soums shall keep registers of income and goods transactions and a book of goods receipts.

Individual entrepreneurs whose income from the sale of goods (works, services) exceeds one billion soums during the calendar year shall pay taxes and mandatory payments in the

manner provided for legal entities and shall maintain accounting in the manner prescribed by law.[8]

Single social payment

The single social payment is paid in a mandatory manner, regardless of the number of days the taxpayer works in a calendar month, as follows:

- 1) by individual entrepreneurs - in an amount not less than the minimum wage per month;
- 2) by individuals who are in labor relations with individual entrepreneurs - in the amount of 50 percent of the minimum salary per month;
- 3) by family members carrying out activities in the form of family business without establishing a legal entity:
 - by a family member registered as an individual entrepreneur - in an amount not less than the minimum wage per month;
 - by other family members (except for those under the age of eighteen) - in the amount of 50% of the minimum salary per month;
- 4) handicraft entities registered and operating in rural areas - by members of the "Craftsman" association - in the amount of 50% of the minimum monthly salary during the first two years of their activity;
- 5) During the working period of the students of the "Master-Apprentice" school until they reach the age of 25 - no less than 2.5 times of the minimum monthly salary per year. The payment of the specified amount of the single social payment is considered as one year when calculating the length of service.[9]

Craftsmen receiving old-age pensions and allowances - members of the "Hunarmand" association are exempted from paying the single social fee.

Persons who have the right to receive an old-age pension, as well as

The amount of the insurance contribution for persons with disabilities of groups I and II must be at least 50% of its specified minimum amount. These benefits are granted on the basis of a pension certificate or a certificate from the medical and labor expert commission.[10]

DISCUSSION

In the economy based on the market economy, the forms of ownership are different, and the income of citizens is formed through different sources. In the taxation of certain sources of income, the system of withholding from the source of payment is insufficient, in general, the system of withholding at the source of payment is not economically justified for business entities in the current conditions, by the tax authorities It was revealed through the analysis that the mechanism of general declaration of income was not introduced in order to constantly control the discrepancy between the incomes and large expenses of the population, which caused the high level of the hidden economy in our country.

Surveys show that, apart from human factors such as failure to fully disclose their income, we can point to the following reasons why citizens do not popularize the current narrow scope of declarations:

1. The presentation of income of the population on the basis of a declaration is not clearly established by legislation, there are a number of benefits regardless of the social status of the population, the amount of income, in particular, the income of self-employed citizens is completely exempt from taxation;

2. Limitation of the possibility of applying sufficient responsibility measures by the tax authorities in the case of determining the untaxed income at the source of payment and not submitting a declaration on the taxation of these incomes;
3. Submission of electronic declaration is done only through electronic key, there is a requirement to upload income documents (taxpayer's obligation to spend additional costs and time in obtaining these documents) to the software product, each case has its own characteristics. that step-by-step clear instructions have not been introduced in the software product;
4. Lack of specialists engaged in providing online advice on the process of filling out the declaration directly in the regional tax authorities;
5. The practice of not taxing when the amount of income of taxpayers, calculated together with the number of their family members, is below the subsistence minimum, the failure to introduce standard deductions for all based on the number of dependent family members of the individual, incomes from citizens to the tax authorities and not keeping track of certain types of expenses (for example, when spent on medical expenses) and, in turn, causing them to not submit a declaration about it.[11]

CONCLUSION

According to the results of the analysis, in the tax policy of our country, the existence of a mechanism for taxation of the population's income on the basis of a general declaration is a necessity, and in order to expand the scope of taxation based on this mechanism, it is advisable to implement the following:

- It is necessary to introduce the practice of taxation through the introduction of the mechanism of gradual general declaration of the income of the population. In this case, it will be applied to all residents first on a voluntary basis, then on a mandatory basis, in the 1st stage (from 2022), according to the incomes and major expenses of government officials, in the 2nd stage (from 2023), the annual turnover is 10 billion. declaration of the income of the founders of business entities over soums, in the 3rd stage (from 2025), to persons who have earned an income higher than 300 times of the minimum annual basic calculation of the population (because the income tax from individuals is withheld at the source of payment regardless of) inclusion in legislation of the obligation to submit a declaration of income to the tax authorities in a mandatory manner;
- In order to unify taxation instead of a fixed tax paid by individual entrepreneurs, to introduce a comprehensive system, a mechanism for income tax on the basis of a declaration, to provide practical assistance to entrepreneurs in the complete management of accounting documents and submission of tax declarations.

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